

ESIP July 2025 Data Governance & Interoperability Session Report

Informed by the Community, for the Community:
A Thematic Framework for Interoperability
to Drive Greater Data Impact

Ge Peng, Sara H. Lubkin, Y. Douglas Rao, Nancy Ritchey, and Emanuel Söding

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Report on the Data Governance & Interoperability Session at the ESIP July 2025 Meeting

Informed by the Community, for the Community: A Thematic Framework for Interoperability to Drive Greater Data Impact

Ge Peng^{1*}, Sara H. Lubkin², Y. Douglas Rao³, Nancy Ritchey⁴, and Emanuel Söding⁵

¹ Science Systems and Applications, Inc. (SSAI)/Contractor to the Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) Project at NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC), Greenbelt, US. ORCID: [0000-0002-1986-9115](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1986-9115)

² NASA GSFC ESDIS, Greenbelt, US. ORCID: [0000-0002-9132-9607](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9132-9607)

³ North Carolina State University, Cooperative Institute for Satellite Earth System Studies (CISESS)/NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI), Asheville, US. ORCID: [0000-0001-6850-3403](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6850-3403)

⁴ Data Stewardship Division, NOAA NCEI, Asheville, US. ORCID: [0000-0003-3939-6287](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3939-6287)

⁵ GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, Kiel, Germany. ORCID: [0000-0002-4467-642X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4467-642X)

* Corresponding author: Ge Peng, ge.peng@ssaihq.com

Key Takeaways

- **Relevance of Data Interoperability:** Enhancing data interoperability through data governance activities is relevant and of interest to the Earth science data management community.
- **Need for Collaboration:** Achieving seamless data interoperability across systems requires sustained collaboration on data governance activities across organizations, disciplines, and domains as well as at all levels of data management and stewardship.
- **Emergence of a Thematic Framework:** A cohesive thematic framework emerged from the responses of attendees at a session in the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) July 2025 Meeting. This framework ties together governance, technical, and cultural and organizational elements to enhance data interoperability and drive greater data impact.

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Abstract

A central challenge for global science is enabling data sharing and reuse across diverse systems. This report details the outcomes of the "*Improving Data Impact through Governance and Stewardship Activities*" session at the ESIP July 2025 Meeting, held both in person at Seattle, WA, US and online everywhere, as a follow-on to the data governance session held at the ESIP July 2024 Meeting.

The July 2025 session focused on leveraging data governance efforts to enhance data interoperability in the Earth science community. Through a collaborative, interactive workshop, participants identified key challenges and corresponding actionable solutions related to interoperability across critical artifacts such as Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), file formats, metadata, and vocabularies. The analysis of discussion outcomes resulted in the emergence of a cohesive thematic framework. This framework integrates three essential and interconnected elements: 1. Governance & Leadership, 2. Technical Infrastructure & Standards, and 3. Cultural & Organizational Practices. Combining all these elements, the framework offers organizations a comprehensive and structured approach to enhancing data interoperability and driving greater data impact.

This report presents both a historical perspective on two consecutive data governance sessions at ESIP and the analysis of outcomes from the 2025 session.

Keywords: ESIP, Data Sharing, Interoperability, Data Governance, Collaboration

1. Background

1.1. About ESIP and ESIP Community

The Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) is a nonprofit organization that comprises more than 170 partner organizations. Supported primarily by US federal Earth science agencies such as the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the United States Geological Survey (USGS), ESIP provides a neutral space and platform for cross-organization and domain collaborations (Shingledecker et al. 2024). Through its regular monthly teleconferences in collaborative areas and semiannual meetings, ESIP brings together domain and data scientists, information specialists, technologists, educators, data and project managers from governmental academic, and private sectors world-wide to collaborate on issues that are relevant to the Earth science community.

1.2. Historical Perspective of the Data Governance Sessions

Data governance encompasses agency policies, standards, and processes that guide data management and stewardship activities. As federal and agency policies evolve to enhance data access to and sharing for federally-funded scientific data and information, the role of data governance becomes increasingly crucial. It provides much needed and practical guidance to agency offices, ensuring their compliance to the policies. The requirements or objectives of data governance in different agencies may overlap. Standardization of data governance practices in those shared data governance objectives could potentially lead to a more efficient and adaptable data governance framework in the Earth science community, but this effort requires cross-agency collaboration.

To explore the existing landscape and discuss what roles ESIP can play in standardizing data governance practices, we organized our first data governance session at the ESIP July 2024 Meeting. An outline of the session is provided below.

1.2.1. Data Governance Session at the ESIP July 2024 Meeting

The first data governance-related session titled “*Fostering Standardization Of Data Governance Practices Across Earth Science Agencies*” was held at the ESIP July 2024 Meeting to explore the shared objectives and disparities in each agency's data governance strategies and discuss how ESIP can play a role in fostering standardization of data governance practices (Peng et al. 2024).

The session consisted of two parts. Following an introduction on definitions and core elements of a typical data governance framework (Figure 1.1, left), invited speakers gave presentations highlighting existing data governance and stewardship activities at NOAA (Morgan 2024), USGS (Hutchison 2024), NASA Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) (Lubkin 2024), and NASA Interagency Implementation and Advanced Concepts Team (IMPACT) (Smith et al. 2024). These presentations provided important information about shared objectives and differences across the agencies' data governance strategies, as summarized in Morgan et al (2024) and recaptured here in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. Core elements of a typical data governance framework (left) and three US Earth science agencies’ strategies (right). Based on: Morgan et al. (2024)

The second part of the ESIP July 2024 Meeting session was designed to explore who is interested in data governance, what data governance means to individual organizations, and understand data governance focus areas and priorities. Slido surveys with carefully formulated questions were carried out during the session. The outcomes were highlighted in the ESIP July 2024 Meeting session (Rao 2025) and recapped below.

1.2.2. Summarization of Survey Results from the ESIP July 2024 Session

What is your main role in your daily job related to data governance?

Figure 1.2. Pie diagram depicting percentage of participants in their roles related to data governance. The total votes are 58.

What does data governance mean to you or your organization in terms of requirements or objectives?

- Framework/structure to guide the improvement of the data ecosystems.
- Policy, principles & standards to enable the implementation.
- People, processes, and technologies on data-related decision making.
- Consistency on data management across organizations and communities.
- Perception of the unfunded mandate/additional requirements.

What are the priority areas of data governance for you?

- Communication and collaboration across the communities
- Developing incentives for data governance
- Connecting with data users to inform data governance
- Change the perception of data governance
- Workforce capacity development for data governance

What can ESIP or other groups help with data governance objectives and priorities?

- Building a community around data governance.
- Facilitating collaboration across different data governance efforts.
- Information sharing on lessons learned.
- Simplifying data governance for projects.

Building a community around data governance and collaborating across the community were the top priorities identified. In response to participants' recommendations to continue the conversation, a follow-on session was held at the ESIP July 2025 Meeting (Lubkin et al. 2025). Data interoperability was selected as the focus area because it is both challenging to address and essential for integrating Earth science data across organizations, which in turn enables broader reuse and greater overall impact. The session outline is provided in the next section.

2. ESIP July 2025 Session Outline

The second session, titled *Improving Data Impact through Governance and Stewardship Activities*, was held at the ESIP July 2025 Meeting. The goal of this session was to examine how connecting data governance and stewardship efforts across organizations can enhance data interoperability and maximize overall impact of Earth science data. Participants discussed data governance-related efforts around PIDs, file formats, metadata, vocabularies, and semantics – critical artifacts that support data interoperability.

The session was designed as an interactive workshop. After a brief introduction was provided to set the context, participants completed a survey that repeated a key question from the ESIP July 2024 Meeting session to assess whether priority areas have shifted. This was followed by an overview of the previous year's survey results, as described in the preceding section. The majority of the session was devoted to a facilitated brainstorming exercise; the methodology is described in the next section, and the outcomes of that activity form the central focus of this report.

3. Methodology

The participants were split into six groups – two online and 4 in the room (Appendix A provides information on the attendees who have signed in.). Each group had participated in two separate parts of the brainstorming session, based on the innovative and creative thinking and problem solving method used in a NASA training offered from NASA's APPEL Knowledge Services (Academy of Program/Project & Engineering Leadership). It in essence follows the workflow illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. Diagram illustrating the collaborative brainstorming workflow based on NASA's APPEL Knowledge Services (Academy of Program/Project & Engineering Leadership) training (generated by chatGPT free version).

The highly engaging session brought together expertise from various organizations and disciplines. The outcomes of innovative brainstorming activities are captured in Appendices B & C. Subsequent analyses were conducted and the results are presented in the next section.

4. Analysis of the Outcomes

As noted in the previous section, the brainstorming activity consisted of two components: Part 1 focused on identifying challenges to improving data interoperability, while Part 2 centered on potential solutions. A prioritization exercise was also conducted for each part with all participants. The resulting inputs are documented in Appendices B and C.

The brainstorming and prioritization outcomes were further analyzed by the authors, with assistance from AI tools, including the free version of ChatGPT. The results of this analysis are described below.

4.1. Analysis Results of Brainstorming – Part 1 Outcomes

Participants explored in depth the challenges associated with enhancing data impact through improved interoperability within the context of data governance activities. A wide range of perspectives was discussed and consolidated within the breakout groups (Appendix B). Notably, participants' understanding of data governance and interoperability appeared to be more mature compared to the previous year.

The Part 1 outcomes were subsequently analyzed using chatGPT, which was prompted to identify key points and common thematic areas. The results of this analysis organize the insights

into three interconnected categories—**Governance, Technical, and Cultural & Organizational**—illustrating how each challenge fits into the broader landscape of interoperability.

4.1.1 Governance & Leadership

Governance and leadership focus on setting direction, defining roles and responsibility, promoting standards, ensuring accountability, and providing resources (Table 4.1).

Table 4.1. Themes, key points, and challenge examples from breakstormings under the Governance & Leadership category

Theme	Key Points	Challenge Examples
Mandates & Leadership Support	Governance initiatives need visible backing from leadership to succeed.	Lack of leadership and mandate; need adequate funding; governance struggles without authority.
Roles & Responsibilities	Clearly defined ownership for making and keeping data interoperable.	“Who is responsible for making data interoperable?”; unclear responsibilities in governance bodies.
Policy & Standards Agreements	Establish cross-organization agreements for standards and compliance.	Agreements across varying datasets; keeping standards relevant to application; managing compliance.
Prioritization & Incentives	Governance must align incentives and priorities to motivate action.	Benefits of interoperability are often delayed; insufficient incentives for documentation and re-curation.

4.1.2. Technical Infrastructure & Standards

This category focuses on tools, formats, and frameworks for achieving interoperability (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2. Themes, key points, and challenge examples from breakstormings under the Technical Infrastructure & Standards category

Theme	Key Points	Challenge Examples
Standardization	Develop and maintain community-accepted, machine-actionable standards.	Community-accepted formats for data/metadata; evolving and competing standards; metadata completeness.

Metadata & Vocabulary	Ensure metadata is clear, complete, and understandable for varied audiences.	Vocabulary definitions for all users; metadata links to references; machine-actionable metadata.
Compatibility & Crosswalks	Address heterogeneous formats, vocabularies, and structures.	Incompatible data structures; complexity of crosswalks; multiple standards across disciplines.
System Modernization	Update legacy systems and hard-coded workflows to support interoperability.	Legacy workflows; code and UI updates needed for new structures.

4.1.3. Cultural & Organizational Practices

This category focuses on people, behaviors, and collaboration across the ecosystem (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3. Themes, key points, and challenge examples from brainstormings under the Cultural & Organizational Practice category

Theme	Key Points	Challenge Examples
Shared Understanding	Build consensus on what “interoperability” means.	Different definitions used by different speakers; need for a common language.
Awareness & Outreach	Promote interoperability concepts internally and externally.	Building awareness in public domain and agencies; limited outreach to potential users.
User-Centered Design	Define interoperability goals through real-world use cases.	Understanding end-user needs; actionable vs. abstract goals.
Collaboration Across Silos	Break down organizational silos for unified governance.	Siloed teams; inconsistent workflows; lack of reliable communication channels.

4.2. Analysis Results of Brainstorming – Part 2 Outcomes

A similar analysis was conducted for the outcomes from Part 2 of the brainstorming activity, which focused on solutions to enhance data impact through improved interoperability. Table 4.4 displays challenges and corresponding actionable solutions side by side, illustrating how recommendations from Part 2 directly address the challenges identified in Part 1.

Table 4.4. Challenges vs solutions for enhancing data interoperability.

Challenges	Solutions
Lack of leadership, mandates, and resources	Seek leadership and funder support, establish mandates, secure funding, and mobilize "champions"
Fragmentation and siloed teams	Foster cross-agency collaboration via ESIP and partnerships
Insufficient or inconsistent standards	Publish and adopt community-agreed standards
Technical incompatibilities (format, vocabularies, tools)	Develop tools for common data models and crosswalks; Use comprehensive, linked PIDs
Poor communication and awareness	Educate data providers on best practices early in the data lifecycle, share success stories and lessons learned, and build cultural buy-in
Limited incentives and competing priorities	Provide incentives, celebrate early adopters; Support metadata harvesting, robust PIDs, and documentation.

Having a thorough understanding of challenges identified in Part 1, along with awareness of community data governance and stewardship practices, provides a strong foundation for recommending corresponding solutions.

Additionally, participants highlighted the need to adopt a user-centered approach by listening to researcher needs for interoperability and to align with international efforts, especially those by standard-setting organizations such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO).

5. A Cohesive Thematic Framework for Interoperability

Integrating outcomes from both parts of the brainstorming activity emerges a thematic framework which is illustrated in Figure 5.1 as a three-circle Venn diagram. Each circle represents a major thematic area essential for achieving interoperability.

Figure 5.1. A Venn diagram that visually ties governance, technical, and cultural elements into a cohesive framework for enhanced interoperability to enable greater data impact. Based on images generated by chatGPT (free version).

5.1. Governance & Leadership

This thematic area focuses on direction, accountability, and resources. Key elements include leadership support, funding, mandates, roles and responsibilities, policy compliance, and international alignment.

5.2. Technical Infrastructure & Standards

This thematic area covers tools, formats, standards, and frameworks. Themes include standards harmonization, common terminology, metadata and documentation, modernized systems, common data models, and crosswalk development.

5.3. Cultural & Organizational Practices

This thematic area centers on people, behaviors, communication, and collaboration. Highlights include shared understanding, training, user-centered approaches and cross-silo collaboration.

5.4. Cross-cutting Insights

Where the circles overlap, the diagram emphasizes:

- Sustained standards and funded technical upgrades.
- User-driven standards, cross-agency partnerships, and early adopter recognition.
- Leadership driving cultural change and promoting best practices.

All these are fundamental in enhanced interoperability through data governance activities, leading to greater data impact.

6. Conclusions and Path Forward

Conclusions based on the results of these sessions are summarized as follows:

- **A Unified Framework for Interoperability:** The core conclusion is the emergence of a cohesive thematic framework for enhanced data interoperability, which ties together three essential and interconnected elements: Governance & Leadership, Technical Infrastructure & Standards, and Cultural & Organizational Practices. This framework is seen as the foundation for achieving greater data impact in the Earth science community.
- **Relevance of Data Interoperability:** The strong participation in and outcomes from both July sessions clearly shows that enhancing data interoperability through data governance activities is relevant and of interest to the Earth science data management community.
- **Maturity of Community Understanding:** The community's understanding of data governance and its role in improving interoperability has matured since the previous year's session, leading to more nuanced identification of both challenges and actionable solutions.
- **Need for Collaborative Action:** The work highlights that overcoming challenges like a lack of leadership mandates, technical incompatibilities, and organizational silos requires sustained efforts in cross-agency collaboration, the adoption of community-agreed standards, and the mobilization of resources and incentives to foster cultural buy-in.

Going forward, to build upon these findings, the authors plan to publish this report to the ESIP Zenodo community and organize a follow-up session at the ESIP July 2026 Meeting. The ultimate goal is to develop formal recommendations for the Earth science community that are expected to have broader relevance across the scientific data stewardship community.

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this report are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of ESIP or the authors' affiliated institutions.

Acknowledgement

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We extend the same appreciation to those who participated in the July 2024 session (Appendix D), especially the presenters, i.e., Jessica Morgan (NOAA), Viv Hutchiso (USGS), Sara Lubkin (NASA ESDIS), and Deborah Smith (NASA IMPACT), for highlighting the perspectives of their respective organizations.

We also extend our sincere thanks to Susan Shingledecker, former ESIP Executive Director, for suggesting the organization of a data governance session for the ESIP July 2024 Meeting. In addition, we appreciate the support provided by the ESIP staff and ESIP fellows for both sessions and acknowledge Lucy Mckenzie for redrawing and improving the presentation of Figure 5.1.

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Appendix A. List of ESIP July 2025 Session Attendees

Table A1. Names and affiliations of participants who have recorded their attendance at the Data Governance & Interoperability session during the ESIP July 2025 Meeting

Name	Affiliation / Location
Bahar Torabi	Ocean Networks Canada/ Victoria, BC
Nancy Ritchey	NOAA NCEI/ Asheville NC
Anne Thessen	UNC
Sara Lubkin	NASA ESDIS / Greenbelt, Maryland
Sarah O'Connor	NOAA NCEI / Silver Spring, MD
Rebecca Hudak	WHOI R2R / Woods Hole, MA
Emanuel Soeding	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration, GEOMAR / Kiel, Germany
Megan Rush	USGS EROS (Contractor) / Sioux Falls, SD
Maricela Abarca	Stanford / virtual - San Francisco, CA
Zachary Medley	ARM Data Center / Oak Ridge, TN
Jerry Carter	EarthScope / Seattle, WA
Jorge Brenner	GCOOS / Houston, TX
Douglas Rao	CISESS-NC & NOAA NCEI / Asheville, NC
Rob Casey	EarthScope Consortium / Seattle, WA
Kate Wing	Intertidal Agency / Oakland, CA
Sarah Menassian	NOAA NCEI / Boulder, CO
Amanda Armstrong	NASA-GSFC / Charlottesville, VA
Aiden Hamade	KSEF - CAPTIVATE Project / Lexington, KY
Matt Mayernik	NSF NCAR / Boulder, CO
Doug Schuster	NSF NCAR / Boulder, CO
Chandra Earl	NEON, ASU / Washington DC
Ken Casey	NOAA NCEI / Silver Spring, MD
Nino Chkhenkeli	AgDataCommons, USDA/Beltsville, MD
Gabriel Kamener	Florida International University (FCE LTER) / Miami, FL
Jessica Morgan	NOAA NESDIS ACIO-s / Silver Spring, MD
Chris Lenhardt	NSF NCAR / Boulder, CO
Stefanie Kethers	ARDC/Australia

Julia Martin	ARDC/Australia
Jens Klump	CSIRO and AuScope / Perth, Australia
Julia Lowndes	Openscapes / California
Ge Peng	SSAI & GSFC ESDIS /Asheville, NC
Yaxing Wei	ORNL DAAC
Katie Hoerberling	Open Environmental Data Project / Oakland, CA
Ingrid Ramos-Guasp	NOAA NESDIS / Silver Spring, MD
Eli Holmes	NOAA Fisheries / Seattle, WA
Karen Stocks	Scripps Inst. of Oceanography / San Diego, CA
Rachael Blake	Intertidal Agency / DC

Appendix B. Outcomes from Brainstorming – Part 1

What are the challenges for enhancing data impact through improved interoperability?

1. Breakout Group - Online 1

- 1.1. Data complexity
- 1.2. Defining interoperability and understanding what that means across multiple organizations
- 1.3. Roles and responsibilities - who is responsible for making data interoperable?
- 1.4. Evolving, and competing, standards, keeping standards relevant to application, reducing friction, managing compliance.
- 1.5. Resources to become compliant/interoperable
- 1.6. Who are the users? Who are we trying to become interoperable with?

2. Breakout Group - Online 2

- 2.1. Theme selling organizations on the importance of data governance
- 2.2. Tend to look at as one size fits all - but data governance exists at all scales from organization to research project
- 2.3. AI summary of our notes below

Five Key Challenges for Enhancing Data Impact through Governance

1. Lack of Leadership and Mandate

Without clear support and directives from management, governance initiatives struggle to gain traction or authority. Need adequate funding

2. Fragmentation and Inconsistency

Siloed teams, inconsistent workflows, and legacy systems make it difficult to implement unified governance practices.

3. Insufficient Standards and Interoperability

Diverse data formats, terminologies, and legal frameworks hinder seamless data sharing and reuse.

4. Limited Capacity and Competing Priorities

A shortage of skilled personnel and lack of time make it hard to prioritize governance amidst other pressing demands.

5. Unclear Communication and Responsibilities

Users lack reliable channels for updates, and governance bodies often lack clearly defined roles and responsibilities

3. Breakout Group - 1 (Upper-Left)

- 3.1. Establishing agreements for standards across varying datasets
- 3.2. Data heterogeneity
- 3.3. Terms of use limitations and licensing issues
- 3.4. Establishing metadata standards and ensuring completeness of metadata
- 3.5. Engrained user (data producer and user) habits -need to support legacy workflows

4. Breakout Group - 2 (Upper-Right)

- 4.1. Common Language; understandable and common across platforms
- 4.2. Traceable/attribution - Making data seamless but also traceable
- 4.3. Community accepted formats for data, metadata content (and standards), data exchange
- 4.4. Building Awareness: getting knowledge of the interoperability out to the public domain (or within agencies)
- 4.5. Metadata must give vocabulary definitions for all users (middle and high school science teacher example); could include link to vocabulary or reference so the length doesn't become a barrier to understanding
- 4.6. Machine actionable metadata
- 4.7.

5. Breakout Group - 3 (Lower-Left)

- 5.1. Resources and incentives for standardization
 - 5.1.1. Different formats/standards accepted/used by different fields
 - 5.1.2. Insufficient incentives (need to give people a reason to spend time and resources on this because benefits come later)
 - 5.1.3. Complexity of building crosswalks, lack of awareness about these
- 5.2. Resources and incentives for documentation
 - 5.2.1. Time needed to make data interoperable or to re-curate it/document it well
 - 5.2.2. Insufficient incentives (need to give people a reason to spend time and resources on this because benefits come later)

6. Breakout Group - 4 (Lower-Right) - back right corner of the room!

- 6.1. Need a reason for interoperability, and clear use cases for what level of interoperability is required. I.e. Understanding end user needs - abstract top-down goal of "interoperability" is harder and not actionable vs a specific use case.
- 6.2. Lack of resources – making data interoperable can mean updating a lot of code and UI that have current structure hard coded.

- 6.3. Incompatible data structures, formats, vocabularies, tools, etc. “the technical side” (this becomes more surmountable with a clear “why”).
- 6.4. Lack of expertise - there may be tools and approaches to make this easier that we don’t know about.
- 6.5. Different definitions of interoperability and speakers are using different definitions

Prioritization:**Most Common**

- Getting management buy-in (Needs to happen at many levels; hard to get buy-in when data governance at your level may not make sense to management).
- Terms of use, licensing, data rights.
- Issues around Standards.
- Common Language; understandable and common across platforms
- Data Heterogeneity.
- Traceable/attributable - Making data seamless but also traceable.
- Lack of resources to change systems that depend on the status quo for a dataset.
- Lack of incentives and resources.

Most Unique

- Building Awareness: getting knowledge of the interoperability out to the public domain (or within agencies).
- Siloed teams, disparate workflows, and outdated systems prevent implementation of unified governance.

Need Most Explanation

- Incompatible data structures, formats, vocabularies, tools, etc. “the technical side” (this becomes more surmountable with a clear “why”).
- Metadata must give vocabulary definitions for all users (middle and high school science teacher example); could include link to vocabulary or reference so the length doesn’t become a barrier to understanding.
- Data governance bodies frequently operate without having clearly defined roles and responsibilities.

Appendix C. Outcomes from Brainstorming – Part 2

What are the things you can do to facilitate DG across agencies and repositories for enhanced data interoperability?

1. Breakout Group - Online 1

- 1.1. Publish community agreed standards
- 1.2. Communicate what resources are available; share use cases and best practice examples.
- 1.3. Funding for data governance
- 1.4. Harmonise data standards - involving the relevant communities
- 1.5. Get the relevant people on board and involved by e.g.
 - 1.5.1. Providing incentives towards sustained and sustainable interoperability (don't just build something, then walk away)
 - 1.5.2. Providing use cases to show the value of interoperability
- 1.6. Make it easy: make sure the underlying data system takes care of all of the sorts of interoperability for them seamlessly
- 1.7. Ensure roles and responsibilities are clear
- 1.8. Listen to what people / researchers need in terms of interoperability
- 1.9. Within organization, find 'champions' in management to make interoperability efforts a priority/get needed resources/'enforce' implementation of requirements
- 1.10. Communication, training & celebrate the early adopters, modeling good data hygiene practices
- 1.11. Setting standards, expectations and leadership support - rules
- 1.12. Get key organisations (funders etc) on board so they provide incentives and possibly mandates etc (carrots & sticks)
- 1.13. Evaluate own initiatives and learn from them, then share the learnings
- 1.14. Publish community agreed standards
- 1.15. Embrace people's concerns and superstitions ;-)

2. Breakout Group - Online 2

- 2.1. Data Governance Stories - Start by focusing on smaller efforts and share any benefits with management (data more easily found and accessed, positive feedback from users, cost savings)
- 2.2. Data governance at all levels
- 2.3. Term "governance" might be misconstrued - Cross-agency at all levels
- 2.4. Overall strategy at agency level
- 2.5. Learn to read your organization. Where are the pain points, what do they want to achieve, how can RDM help them with that.

3. Breakout Group - 1 (Upper-Left)

- 3.1. Tools to create common data models
- 3.2. Establish standard APIs, PIDs
- 3.3. Support metadata harvesting
- 3.4. Take a standardization-first approach
- 3.5. Show standards by examples
- 3.6. Advocate for standards and interoperability
- 3.7. Apply/enforce agreed upon standards within a domain repository
- 3.8. Thorough documentation

4. Breakout Group - 2 (Upper-Right)

- 4.1. Work within international organizations to establish DG standards.
- 4.2. Intentionally collaborate and innovate with other agency partners.
- 4.3. De-silo working groups and webinar series to be inter-agency partnerships
- 4.4. Discuss these topics via ESIP
- 4.5. Work with data providers to be standards compliant when data are originally generated
- 4.6. Work with funders to establish clearer rules and expectations for data management, metadata, etc, that is generated via their funding

5. Breakout Group - 3 (Lower-Left)

- 5.1. Good metadata standard formats
- 5.2. Accept that no repository will have perfectly interoperable data unless it's small – even within repos, different vocabularies → leave it to communities
- 5.3. Share language to support advocates getting interop language into public comments
- 5.4. Share success stories and stories of the impacts of lack of interop
- 5.5. Work with repositories that have robust interop practices in place
- 5.6. The archiving group currently doesn't have standards for interop like use of PIDs. Adopting existing metadata standards; 'concept DOIs' to support versioning and provenance
 - 5.6.1. How to link DOIs for archived datasets that we've had to separate due to repo size limits?
- 5.7. Crosswalk development and sharing those

6. Breakout Group - 4 (Lower-Right)

- 6.1. Work to educate data providers on best practices, to foster interoperability
- 6.2. Do better with comprehensive PIDs - don't create new PIDs when unnecessary
- 6.3. Adopt community/existing DG policies, standards when possible over inventing new

- 6.4. Come to ESIP! Contribute to community efforts as time/resources allow
- 6.5. Checkout Openscapes organization and their framework

Prioritization

Most Challenging

- Agency strategies.
- Weed out repetitive standards, align with one.
- Crosswalk development.
- Cultural change.

Most Impactful

- Identifying all relevant players and getting them to sit on the same table.
- Listen, evaluate, share and apply learnings - **this is also a low-hanging fruit.**
- Get funders etc on board.
- Work within international organizations to establish DG standards.
- Apply/Enforce agreed upon standards within a domain repository.
- Info materials and tailored training about key data governance concepts (such as PIDs).

Low Hanging Fruit

- Tell data governance stories.
- Listen, evaluate, share and apply learnings - **repeat from most impactful.**
- Adopt community/existing DG policies, standards when possible over inventing new.

Appendix D. List of ESIP July 2024 Session Attendees

Table D1. Names and affiliations of participants who have recorded their attendance at the Data Governance session during the ESIP July 2024 Meeting

Name	Affiliation / Location
Ge Peng	UA Huntsville & MSFC IMPACT/ Huntsville, AL
Viv Hutchison	US Geological Survey / Denver, CO
Jessica Morgan	NOAA NESDIS / Silver Spring, MD
Sara Lubkin	NASA ESDIS/ Greenbelt, MD
Bruce Wilson	ORNL DAAC/ Oak Ridge, TN
Kyle Metta	NOAA OAR / Harrisonburg, VA
Kathe Todd-Brown	University of Florida / Gainesville, FL, USA
Chenyue Jiao	University of Illinois Urbana Champaign
Colleen Rosales	OpenAQ and UC Davis
Lucy Bastin	Aston University / Birmingham, UK
Laura Brenskelle	NOAA IOOS / Asheville, NC
Ann Vega	USEPA / Cincinnati, OH
Austin Lowe	AAAS WNC / Asheville, NC
Shannon Leslie	NSIDC DAAC / Boulder, CO
Candida Dewes	NSIDC DAAC / Boulder, CO
Rachael Blake	Intertidal Agency / Maryland
April Lamb	NCICS / Asheville, NC
Stephanie M. Wingo	NASA IMPACT, ADMG, UAH / Huntsville, AL
Meredith Goins	World Data System (WDS-IPO) / Knoxville, TN
Megan Buzanowicz	ASDC DAAC/ Hampton, VA
Lori Hager	NOAA NCEI/ Asheville, NC
Douglas Rao	CISESS-NC & NOAA-NCEI/ Asheville, NC

Savannah Lewis	University of California, San Diego/ San Diego, CA
Doug Schuster	NSF-NCAR / Boulder, CO
Charley Haley	Wayforagers / Olympia, WA
Daniela Santos Oliveira	WDS / Knoxville, TN
Saebuyul Choe	LDEO/ Brooklyn, NY
Nazila Merati	NCEI/Boulder, CO, Seattle, WA
Tamar Norkin	USGS / Denver, CO
Tammy Walker	ORNL DAAC/ Oak Ridge, TN
Steve Olding	NASA ESDIS / Arlington, VA
Joseph Gum	NSF NCAR / Boston, MA
Rudi Gens	Alaska Satellite Facility / Fairbanks, AK
Terri Velliquette	ORNL / Oak Ridge, TN
Mark Parsons	ODATA / Boulder, CO
Ingrid Ramos-Guasp	NOAA NESDIS / Silver Spring, MD
Angela Sallis	NOAA NCEI GDIT/Stennis Space Center, MS
John Graybeal	GO FAIR US / Mountain View, CA
Jeff Arnfield	NOAA NCEI / Asheville NC
Nancy Ritchey	NOAA NCEI / Asheville NC
Melissa Smuck	NOAA GOMO / Pulaski, PA
Rebecca Ringuette	NASA GSFC HDRL / Greenbelt, MD
Noriko Shoji	NOAA Fisheries / Seattle, WA
John Relph	NOAA NCEI / he/him / Silver Spring, MD
Brandon Whitehead	University of Florida / Palmerston North